

NFDI4Earth

Deliverable D1.3.9

Evaluation of NFDI4Earth education training events based on NFDI4Earth educational resources

Remon Sadikni ,
Kemeng Liu , Farzaneh Sadeghi

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Executive summary

This report presents a common questionnaire for evaluating NFDI4Earth training courses, covering both online courses on the EduPortal platform and in-person EduHub events such as workshops and summer schools. The questionnaire evaluates teaching materials, lecturers, participant background, and general settings. Evaluation results from four training events are presented, demonstrating the practical application of this approach. The questionnaire will be used in EduTrain (online) courses and events in the future to ensure high-quality training in research data management for the Earth System Sciences community.

Abbreviations

D1.3.15 – Concept for establishing and maintaining a network of NFDI4Earth education and training sites (EduHubs)

EduHubs – A network of NFDI4Earth education and training sites

EduPortal – An online platform for NFDI4Earth training courses, see <https://edutrain.nfdi4earth.de/>

EduTrain – Education and Training Materials and Services, see <https://www.nfdi4earth.de/2participate/education-training>

ES – Earth System

ESS – Earth System Sciences

FAIR – Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability

HSBO – Bochum University of Applied Sciences

LMS – Learning Management System

M1.3 – Measure 1.3: Education and Training Materials and Services

NFDI – National Research Data Infrastructure (Nationale Forschungsdaten Infrastruktur), see <http://www.nfdi.de>

NFDI4Earth – NFDI Consortium Earth System Sciences / NFDI Konsortium Erdsystemforschung, see <https://www.nfdi4earth.de/>

OER – Open Educational Resources

RDM – Research Data Management

TA – Task Area

TUM – Technische Universität München

UNIHH – Universität Hamburg

UNIMS – Universität Münster

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1. Introduction

The goal of this report is to present a common questionnaire for evaluating NFDI4Earth training courses. These education activities provide online and in-person training in the area of research data management in the earth system sciences. Apart from developing the EduPortal platform, which offers online courses, the EduTrain team members host EduHub events such as workshops and summer schools (see D1.3.15). To ensure that the provided courses and teaching events (e.g., workshops, lectures, etc.) meet the needs of the recipients and are effectively contributing to the recipients' learning experience, we conduct evaluations of the provided events.

2. Theoretical basis of teaching evaluation

Evaluation of teaching activities is an empirical investigation and systematic analysis of the teaching concepts, requirements, processes, and effects. It provides valuable feedback regarding the quality and outcomes of the learning materials, and serves as a basis for further improvement. From a theoretical point of view, evaluation can be seen as a form of problem-solving strategy which aims at delivering reliable empirical data and decomposing complex problems to make rational decisions on teaching processes (Rindermann 2001, 2003).

There are usually three types of evaluation: self-evaluation, external evaluation, and student evaluation. In self-evaluation, teaching personnel assess their own performance, while external evaluation is conducted by experts. However, in this report, we will focus on the third type of evaluation, student evaluation, where the assessment is provided by the participants of the courses or training events. Student evaluation can be conducted in different formats, the most prominent examples are open interviews and questionnaires. There is a wide variety of questionnaires, in the most basic form, the questions about successful learning (or teaching) can be classified in 4 categories:

1. the material (complete, up-to-date, understandable)
2. the teacher (clarity, motivation, competence),
3. the student (motivation, pre-existing knowledge, absence),
4. and the general setting (media facilities, size of audience).

Of course, these categories can be subdivided to a much higher extent, but for our purpose this classification is sufficient.

3. Evaluation method

We envisioned a simple common evaluation questionnaire that the course participants can fill out after the course. A challenge in evaluating teaching events in the context of NFDI4Earth is that the format of events might vary, meaning that the courses can include self-learning material but also lectures and workshops held by a teacher. In order to find a set of questions for these different events, we made use of the fact that every institution of the EduTrain team has experience in providing and evaluating ESS teaching events. Our approach was to compare and eventually merge the different questionnaires we used in our EduTrain activities. In the following, we start with the evaluation form of online courses and then we extend this one to get a complete form for EduHub events.

4. Evaluation form for online courses

The online courses in our EduPortal have two functions:

1. They can be used as a self-learning resource.
2. They back up the EduHub events with training material.

In this paragraph, we show the questionnaire for the self-learning resources, the second case will be described in detail in sec. 5. The seven questions for the online courses are shown in Tab. 1.

Table 1: Evaluation form for online courses

Question (rating: 1=not at all, 7=perfect)	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1. Overall, how do you like the course?							
2. The structure is logical / clear.							
3. The content is illustrated with examples.							
4. Difficulty of the content: 1=far too easy, 4=perfect, 7=far too difficult.							
5. Speed of the teaching: 1=far too slow, 4=perfect, 7=far too fast.							
6. My previous knowledge was: 1=too little to follow, 4=perfectly sufficient, 7=I knew everything before.							
7. Theory and practice are linked.							

While the first question is about the overall perception of the course, all the other questions deal with the quality and classification of the training material. Only in question 6, we incorporate the previous knowledge of the course participants to get feedback about the difficulty level. The rating has 7 possible nuances from “not at all” to “perfect”; in case the rating deviates from the norm, the meaning of the numbers 1 to 7 is defined in the question (4, 5, 6).

5. Evaluation form for EduHub events

For the evaluation of EduHub events, we need additional questions about the quality of the teacher and, if the course takes place in-person, of the equipment in the class room.

The first 7 questions of the evaluation form of Tab. 1 are extended by the questions shown in Tab. 2.

Table 2: Additional evaluation questions for EduHub events

Question (rating: 1=not at all, 7=perfect)	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
8. There are enough tutors present.							
9. The lecturers seem well prepared.							
10. The lecturers manage their time well.							
11. It is important for the lecturers that participants learn something.							
12. Accompanying documents and materials are accessible, complete, useful and up-to-date.							
13. The equipment is in good condition.							
14. What did you like about the workshop?							
15. What can be improved about the workshop?							

Questions 9, 10, 11 are about the quality of the lecturer(s), question 12 deals with the quality of the accompanying material. In case the event takes place in-person, questions 8 and 13 come into play asking for the satisfaction with the general setting in the course room. At the end of the questionnaire, there are 2 questions where participants can enter free text to share some thoughts about what was right and what was wrong about the event. The complete questionnaire including the first 7 questions can be found in Tab. 9. With these questions we cover all 4 aspects of training events that we discussed in section 2.

6. Evaluation results of training events

In the already given training events, we used different evaluation methods and forms to gain experience on their respective advantages and disadvantages. The recently merged questionnaire shown in this report was only used once (see 6.3) up to now, but will be applied from now on to every course. In this section, we will show the evaluation results of the following events:

1. Exercises for “Image Analysis for Mapping” at the Technical University of Munich during the winter semester of 2022/2023
2. PhD course “Python for Geospatial Analysis” at Aalborg University Copenhagen, held from 24th to 26th April 2023
3. Workshops “How to create publishable netCDF data” conducted by the Integrated Climate Data Center, University Hamburg in 2023 and 2024
4. Workshop “Spatial Data Science across Languages (SDSL)” conducted by University Münster on September 18th-19th.

6.1. Evaluation of “Image Analysis for Mapping” exercises

In 2022, the project “Coding4Geo” was funded and developed as one of our educational pilots (Tab. 3). Post-development, the material has been successfully integrated into the “Image Analysis for Mapping,” lecture offered during the winter semester as part of the Cartography M.Sc. program at the Technical University of Munich. Subsequently, a comprehensive evaluation process was carried out by the course organizer to assess the effectiveness and impact of the course materials. To do so, they used their evaluation template, which shared considerable similarities with the NFDI4Earth evaluation survey.

The University of Munich's evaluation process has provided valuable insights into the effectiveness of the course material. Below are the outcomes of the evaluation related to the portion of material covered by the Coding4Geo project:

- Structure of content: students unanimously believed that the contents of the course logically build on each other.
- Clarity of learning outcomes: the intended learning outcomes were found to be clearly defined in the course description, as unanimously agreed upon by students.
- Roll of exercises: students universally believed that the exercise modules contributed to a deeper understanding of the subject matter.
- Comprehension: all participants indicated their ability to reproduce key concepts from this module.

- Skill building: 92.9% of students stated improved proficiency in the skills associated with the subject matter.
- Application: 85.7% of the students reported feeling confident in handling typical tasks in the subject area after completing the course.
- Qualitative feedback on Coding4Geo content: the following feedback was collected in the form of free text format regarding the Coding4Geo content:

“The exercises were not too difficult and had just the right amount of challenge. The instructions and tips provided in the exercises were also helpful to complete the tasks.”

“The course was really useful and helped a lot in understanding the basic image analysis operations. Exercises were well-balanced between “here is the task, google everything by yourself” and “here is almost the whole code written for you, just change the few variables”, which is really appreciated.”

“The exercises made the content of the lecture very clear and were well chosen.”

“The exercises are super helpful for understanding all the theory in practice.”

“Good structure, helps to understand concepts that were presented in the lecture.”

Several students articulated a need for more foundational knowledge of Python programming to refresh their knowledge. To meet this need, the “Python Onboarding” course was developed as a comprehensive, self-paced online resource.

Table 3: “Image Analysis for Mapping” course description

Attribute	Description
Course Type	Regular lecture exercises
Course Level	Cartography M.Sc.
Offering Institute	Technical University of Munich
Course Description	Geospatial data analysis covering: (1) Basic image processing (transformation, filtering, segmentation); (2) Machine Learning for geospatial data (supervised/unsupervised methods, regression); (3) Spatial-temporal data analysis (clustering, interpolation)

The Coding4Geo project will also be available on our online educational portal, along with the NFDI4Earth evaluation form. This ensures a continuous feedback loop, enabling iterative refinement of the content based on learner inputs and experiences.

6.2. Evaluation of PhD course “Python for Geospatial Analysis”

Our goal in developing course content is to create materials that are as accessible and reusable as possible, suited for both self-learning and guided-learning purposes. We are in the process of publishing a series of spatial data analysis courses using Python language on our e-learning portal, which will range from the basics of Python to advanced methods, such as using machine learning techniques for the analysis of Earth observation data.

The course “Python for Spatial Data Analysis” is a successful example of what we are aiming to achieve. This course aims to familiarize researchers, mainly young PhD students, with doing tasks traditionally conducted in a desktop GIS system using Python to achieve faster, more flexible, and completely reproducible results, which is one of the main objectives of the NFDI project (Tab. 4).

Taking advantage of a three-day PhD course titled “Python for Geospatial Analysis,” from the 24th to the 26th of April 2023 at Aalborg University in Copenhagen (AAU CPH), we were able to test and receive feedback on these materials. This course at AAU wasn't directly tied to NFDI4Earth and was primarily an opportunity to refine the content based on real-world application and feedback. Following the event, the organizers conducted a thorough evaluation. The following are the evaluation outcomes regarding the course content:

- Overall satisfaction: the course was universally perceived as satisfactory by all participating students, reflecting a positive reception of the material.
- Clarity of course description: a substantial 94% of students acknowledged the clear definition of the intended learning outcomes and the difficulty level in the course description.
- Workload: 77% of the students managed to comprehend the course content with minimal to no difficulties within the estimated study time. The remaining 23% experienced minor challenges in keeping up with the content within the estimated study time.

Several students have expressed a need for auxiliary learning materials, such as cheat sheets for basic Python syntax and the libraries used throughout the course. In response, we have initiated the development of these supplementary tools, which will be integrated into the course materials once they are made available online. These resources aim to serve as quick references and support tools for students as they navigate through the course content.

Table 4: “Python for Geospatial Analysis” course description

Attribute	Description
Course Type	Lecture, exercises
Course Level	PhD

Attribute	Description
Offering Institute	Aalborg University
Course Description	Introduction to Python for mapping, exploring, processing, and analysing geospatial information. Covers transferring desktop GIS tasks to Python for faster, more flexible, and reproducible results. Topics: (1) General introduction to Python and explorative analysis; (2) Vector-based geospatial analysis; (3) Raster-based geospatial analysis. Uses modules like fiona, geopandas, pysal, and rasterio.

The course was attended by individuals from a wide range of backgrounds, each with varying levels of experience and skills. With such a diverse group, the learning environment was naturally characterized by a broad spectrum of needs and expectations. While creating content to cater to such a varied audience can be challenging, the majority of responses were favorable, reflecting the material's inclusive and comprehensive nature.

The course "Python for Spatial Data Analysis" course will soon be accessible on our online educational portal, supplemented by the NFDI4Earth evaluation form. This continuous feedback mechanism allows for ongoing refinement of the content, influenced by learner inputs and experiences.

6.3. Evaluation of workshop "How to create publishable netCDF data"

In July 2023 and in July 2024, the EduTrain members from Hamburg University conducted an in-person EduHub workshop with the title "How to create publishable netCDF data". This workshop has been especially created in the frame of NFDI4earth to foster the publication of earth system science data (ESS). It explains the creation of CF compliant netCDF files - one of the most important formats in ESS. Further information on this workshop, including a detailed description can be found in Tab. 5.

Table 5: "How to Create Publishable netCDF Data" workshop description

Attribute	Description
Course Type	Workshop
Course Level	ESS doctoral candidates
Offering Institute	University of Hamburg
Course Description	Creating publishable netCDF (Network Common Data Format) data from the Earth System Sciences. Focus on creating CF (Climate and Forecast) compliant netCDF files. Participants bring their own data or use provided datasets. Prerequisites: Python programming skills. Includes introduction to netCDF format, CF conventions, and hands-on practice.

The evaluation of the first workshop in 2023 was based on the evaluation questionnaire of the MIN-Faculty at Hamburg University. This questionnaire was a modified version of the HILVE

questionnaire (Rindermann 1996, Rindermann 2001). Our questionnaire (Tab. 7) contained 25 aspects which can be rated by the participants from 1 to 7, and constituted the basis of the merged questionnaire (Tab. 9). The overall result of the workshop evaluation was very positive.

In the second workshop in 2024, we already used the merged evaluation form, the results from the 10 participants are shown in Fig. 1. The outcome shows that the participant really liked the workshop. What we could improve is the equipment and condition of our class room (see result of the last question 13) although the rating is still good. In the free text forms we also got valuable results: Some participants mentioned the good mix of theory and practice. Some really liked the possibility to work on their own data. The bad air condition of the room was brought up, too, which fits to the slightly negative results of question 13.

6.4. Evaluation of workshop “Spatial Data Science across Languages (SDSL)”

The Spatial Data Science across Languages (SDSL) workshop was conducted by the EduTrain members at the University of Münster on the 18th-19th of September 2023 as a hybrid EduHub event. The goal of the SDSL workshop was to look at differences and commonalities in the approaches towards various aspects of spatial data science taken by the scripting languages R, Julia, and Python¹. Further information on this workshop can be found in Tab. 6.

The workshop was evaluated by using the questionnaire in Tab. 8. The post-workshop evaluation survey had nearly equal participation from both online and in-person attendees, with a high response rate of approximately 90%.

- Overall satisfaction: the vast majority of participants were satisfied with the workshop (94.3%) and almost all indicated they would recommend it to others if the opportunity arose.
- Organization: the feedback was highly positive regarding the workshop's level of organization, with 82.8% of participants expressing satisfaction with the amount of information provided in advance to help them prepare.
- Qualitative feedback on the workshop in 2023:
 - Enjoyed aspects: with overwhelmingly positive feedback, the key highlights enjoyed by the participants were the friendly and open atmosphere, fostering deep connections and discussions among participants from the diverse communities of Python, R, Julia, and Rust. They appreciated the high technical depth, the focus on key issues, and the opportunity to learn directly from the maintainers of critical packages in the geospatial sphere. The workshop's organization, timely and practical topics, and conversational format encouraging free-flowing ideas were highly valued as opposed to “merely listening to presenters recite previously

Figure 1: Evaluation results of the netCDF workshop 2024, the questions 4-6 are centered scores where the best score is 4. The highest score for all other questions is 7.

published or upcoming work”. Participants also enjoyed the chance to explore different approaches, learn from one another, and gain insights into low-level standards, spatial libraries, and geospatial software development. The following is some of the collected feedback in the form of free text format:

“This was a unique opportunity to bring the main developers of geospatial software together and discuss low-level standards. I think this is of great importance not only from a developer perspective but also from a user perspective, to understand the commonalities but also the bottlenecks for the different communities.”

“A wide range of attendees, an exciting dev-friendly dive into Julia, an injection of Rust and involvement of ESA”

- Suggested future improvements: the participants described the workshop as a strong first effort, with suggested improvements to enhance future editions. Many recommended adding more structure to the second edition, such as lightning talks, breakout sessions, hackathons, or code sprints, while still fostering active participation. More user-focused content, like use cases and user stories, were proposed to complement the developer-centered discussions. Inclusivity was another focus, with suggestions to directly invite more women developers, even if they are not core package contributors. Encouraging broader participation by sharing facilitation roles and allowing more space for others to contribute was also highlighted. Although online participants appreciated the possibility to join remotely, they emphasized the need for better audio-visual systems to improve accessibility and suggested sharing discussion topics and background materials in advance to streamline sessions, for example:

“Short pitches where people are informed previously, i.e. to prepare how something is implemented in a specific package or language, could be of advantage.”

Table 6: “Spatial Data Science across Languages” workshop description

Attribute	Description
Course Type	Workshop
Offering Institute	University of Münster
Target Group	Software developers and users
Course Description	Exploring differences and commonalities in spatial data science approaches across Python, Julia, and R. Topics include: vector data cubes, vector data encodings (WKB, geoarrow/geoparquet, CF), spherical geometry, packaging with GDAL/PROJ/GEOS dependencies, large data cubes and APIs, interoperability and file formats, aligning teaching materials, and community dynamics.

This feedback was highly valuable and encouraged the second edition in the series of the SDSL workshops to be organized internationally incorporating the suggested improvements on the 18th-19th of September 2024 at the Geographical Institute of the Charles University, Prague, Czechia. The evaluation questionnaire was also forwarded and adapted for use by the organizers at Charles University of Prague.

7. Outlook

Up to now, we developed a common questionnaire for evaluating our EduTrain Courses by the participants. The next step is to use this evaluation form for every online course and every EduHub event so that we get comparable evaluation results for securing a high quality level. In the future, we will use feedback of our participants about the questionnaire to improve our concept.

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A. Appendix

Evaluation questionnaire for the netCDF workshop in 2023

Table 7: Evaluation questionnaire used for the netCDF workshop in 2023

Question	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
The course structure is logical / clear. (1=not at all, 7=perfect)							
The importance / relevance of the contents is made clear. (1=not at all, 7=perfect)							
The content is illustrated with examples. (1=not at all, 7=perfect)							
Difficulty of the content: 1=far too easy, 4=perfect, 7=far too difficult.							
Speed of the teaching: 1=far too slow, 4=perfect, 7=far too fast.							
My previous knowledge was: 1=too little to follow, 4=perfectly sufficient, 7=I knew everything.							
The content corresponds to its title and description. (1=not at all, 7=perfect)							
Theory and practice are linked. (1=not at all, 7=perfect)							
The tasks / presentation topics are relevant. (1=not at all, 7=perfect)							
There are enough tutors present. (1=not at all, 7=perfect)							
The lecturers speak clearly (speed, volume, language skills). (1=not at all, 7=perfect)							
The lecturers are able to explain complicated issues. (1=not at all, 7=perfect)							
The lecturers seem well prepared. (1=not at all, 7=perfect)							
The lecturers manage their time well. (1=not at all, 7=perfect)							
The lecturers are dedicated and convey enthusiasm. (1=not at all, 7=perfect)							
The lecturers encourage students' questions and active participation. (1=not at all, 7=perfect)							
The lecturers are friendly in teacher-student interaction. (1=not at all, 7=perfect)							
The lecturers moderate discussions well. (1=not at all, 7=perfect)							
It is important for the lecturers that students learn something. (1=not at all, 7=perfect)							
Accompanying documents and materials are accessible, complete, useful and up-to-date. (1=not at all, 7=perfect)							
I have learned a lot taking this course. (1=not at all, 7=perfect)							
In this course, I learned more: 1=from the lecturers, 7=by myself.							
The room is suitable (windows, accessibility, visibility). (1=not at all, 7=perfect)							
There is enough equipment for each participant. (1=not at all, 7=perfect)							
The equipment is in good condition. (1=not at all, 7=perfect)							

Evaluation questionnaire for “Spatial Data Science across Languages (SDSL)” workshop

Location: Institute of Geoinformatics, University of Münster

Workshop Homepage: <https://r-spatial.org/sdsl/>

Form prepared by: Yomna Eid

Response rate: 90%

Table 8: Evaluation questionnaire for SDSL workshop

Question	Response Type
Name	<i>(optional)</i>
How did you participate? (a) Online, (b) In-person	<i>(multiple-choice)</i>
How likely is it that you would recommend the SDSL workshop to a friend or colleague? (1=Not at all likely, 10=Extremely likely)	<i>(scale 1 to 10)</i>
Overall, how would you rate the workshop? (a) Excellent, (b) Very good, (c) Good, (d) Fair, (e) Poor	<i>(multiple-choice)</i>
What did you like about the workshop?	<i>(free-text)</i>
What can be improved about the workshop?	<i>(free-text)</i>
How organized was the workshop? (a) Extremely organized, (b) Very organized, (c) Somewhat organized, (d) Not so organized, (e) Not organized at all	<i>(multiple-choice)</i>
Prior to the workshop, how much information that you needed did you get? (a) All, (b) Most, (c) Some, (d) Little, (e) None	<i>(multiple-choice)</i>
What did you think about the length of the workshop in proportion to the content? (a) Much too long, (b) Too long, (c) About right, (d) Too short, (e) Much too short	<i>(multiple-choice)</i>
Is there anything else you would like to share about the workshop?	<i>(free-text)</i>

Merged evaluation form

Table 9: Merged evaluation form for EduHub events

Question (rating: 1=not at all, 7=perfect)	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1. Overall, how do you like the workshop?							
2. The structure is logical / clear.							
3. The content is illustrated with examples.							
4. Difficulty of the content: 1=far too easy, 4=perfect, 7=far too difficult.							
5. Speed of the teaching: 1=far too slow, 4=perfect, 7=far too fast.							
6. My previous knowledge was: 1=too little to follow, 4=perfectly sufficient, 7=I knew everything.							
7. Theory and practice are linked.							
8. There are enough tutors present.							
9. The lecturers seem well prepared.							
10. The lecturers manage their time well.							
11. It is important for the lecturers that participants learn something.							
12. Accompanying documents and materials are accessible, complete, useful and up-to-date.							
13. The equipment is in good condition.							
14. What did you like about the workshop?							
15. What can be improved about the workshop?							